

Local Covariance Equalization of Hyperspectral Imagery: Advantages and Limitations for Target Detection

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Abstract—¹²The operational implementation of many conventional hyperspectral detection algorithms can be greatly simplified by adaptively preprocessing all test pixels and target signatures to equalize first- and second-order background statistics. The process is equivalent to expressing spectral radiance in a locally Euclidean coordinate system. Removing hyperspectral curvature in this way greatly simplifies both the data archiving function and the mathematical forms of standard detectors. Here we show why the equalization procedure does not compromise performance for conventional detection methods. More advanced algorithms cannot, however, be implemented with equalized data alone. We show how this limitation can nonetheless be overcome by temporarily storing a few parameters, with no archiving penalty.

applications, among which is a change detection technique that can distinguish arrivals from departures.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	1
2. REAL TIME ADAPTIVE BACKGROUND MODELING ..	2
3. DETECTION ALGORITHMS	3
4. WARHORSE DETECTION	6
5. SUMMARY	7
6. REFERENCES	8

2. REAL TIME ADAPTIVE BACKGROUND

MODELING

WARHORSE Real Time Processor: System Overview

NRL's WARHORSE real-time processor (RTP) acquires and records data from the WARHORSE sensors (Fig. 1), implements real-time algorithms for sensor data correction, target detection and cueing, image chipping, and image geo-registration. It also provides for real-time operator control and data display. Progressively enhanced versions of the WARHORSE RTP have been successfully operated during multiple data collection and demonstration experiments on board various platforms including Twin Otter, King Air, and P-3 aircraft as well as a Predator UAV.

1. INTRODUCTION

The US Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) has developed advanced signal processing algorithms for remote hyperspectral target detection. These are realized in autonomous sensor systems equipped with real time onboard image and signal processors that implement adaptive detection algorithms, along with atmospheric compensation techniques and data preprocessing and calibration functions. The signal processing architecture of the current suite of detection algorithms has been erected on a foundation formed from a particular image-based hyperspectral signature prediction procedure that fortuitously simplifies algorithm implementation. This paper describes that architecture and derives the mathematical forms of the algorithms. Advanced detection methods are described in a similar context. These include multi-temporal

Figure 1. WARHORSE Real-Time Signal Processor.

The RTP consists of three primary subsystems as diagrammed in Figure 1: the Sensor Interface Computer (SIC), the Data Processing Computer (DPC) and the Operator Display Computer (ODC). The Sensor Interface Computer (SIC) is a ruggedized PC-based chassis that uses COTS frame grabbers to acquire data from the VNIR hyperspectral imaging (HSI) camera and a panchromatic HRI line-scanner. It also acquires sensor position and attitude data from a co-mounted CMIGITS-3 GPS/INS unit via a serial interface.

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A custom PMC board with a Xilinx FPGA is used for event capture synchronized to GPS time, to enable subsequent association of camera frames and GPS/INS data for precision image geolocation. This function is required by an NRL change detection algorithm, so that anomalous pixel-level hyperspectral signal changes occurring over (typically) 24-hour periods can be identified. These correspond to thematic image changes (usually the movement of an object), as distinct from those associated with temporal variability in atmosphere or scene illumination. The SIC sends raw formatted HSI, HRI and support data to the DPC for processing across a 100 Mbyte/sec Fibre-Extreme interface. The total input data rate to the DPC is approximately 12 Mbyte/sec.

The DPC chassis is a custom enclosure with a five-slot VME backplane and a SCSI removable four-drive data recording system with 144 GBytes total capacity. The DPC implements on-board, real-time sensor data processing functions in six G4 Altivec compute nodes with bulk RAM interconnected by the Mercury Race++ switched-fabric backplane. A Motorola 5110 G4 single-board computer serves as run-time host for the Mercury system, and performs various functions including interface handling, data recording, chip generation, and formatting and compression of display products and target cues.

The DPC sends pseudo-color HSI, detected target cues, HRI target chips, GPS/INS data and sensor telemetry to the ODC by Ethernet cable or a custom 2 Mbit/sec RS-170 RF digital modem. The RF video downlink is used for UAV-based applications where the ODC is located at a ground control site.

The ODC is a Windows PC with dual color monitors and local disk storage. It implements the operator control GUIs and real-time displays for the WARHORSE system. The ODC simultaneously generates and presents several types of real-time displays, including:

- (a) HSI raw data waterfall display;
- (b) System status and parameter displays;
- (c) HSI GeoPaint Display, which shows false-color HSI and target cue symbology being geo-registered in real-time onto a UTM ground coordinate grid;
- (d) Target Chip Display, which shows target cue information and geo-registered image “chips” centered on detected targets, and presented as panchromatic HRI, false-color HSI, or pan-sharpened HSI.

Local Whitening of Hyperspectral Background Imagery

The WARHORSE DPC implements hyperspectral data correction and covariance-based target detection algorithms (see §3) using a block-oriented processing approach diagrammed in Figure 2. A moving window composed of multiple blocks of spectral imagery defined along the pushbroom direction of flight is used to adaptively estimate

scene statistics (spectral mean and covariance matrix) and to calculate the detection filter to be applied to data in a selected “detection block” (Figure 2). The window and the detection block are then moved ahead one block interval for the next compute cycle. Depending on the particular application, the detection block can be positioned ahead of or inside the statistics window, and in the latter case it may be included in or excluded from that window. Typical statistics window lengths are on the order of several hundred HSI lines.

Figure 2. Block-oriented processing concept for WARHORSE pushbroom HSI data.

Following Level 1 correction and buffering of the HSI data in a block, the block spectral mean and covariance are adaptively estimated by pixel averaging and combined with similar statistics from other blocks in the current window to update the background statistics. Block-indexed statistics are maintained in a data buffer available to each processor. The updated window covariance matrix is then eigen-factored to generate principal component (PC) eigenvectors and eigenvalues, which are used to project and “whiten” mean-centered spectral data vectors in the current detection block. (The purpose of this operation is described below.) The whitened data are then used to compute detector (i.e., detection algorithm) outputs, which are CFAR-thresholded (constant false alarm rate) and spatially filtered to generate target cues.

Most of the hyperspectral target detection algorithms implemented in the system can be interpreted as converting the sensed radiance at a test pixel into a scalar distance: measured from the local background mean in the case of anomaly detection; from a mean target signal in signature-based methods. Before whitening, the distance metric is non-Euclidean, described by the non-negative symmetric covariance matrix associated with the current statistics window. As the window progresses over the background, so does the estimated covariance matrix, meaning that the metric is variable and, therefore, not flat. The whitening operation modifies the test signals to convert all distance measures computed by the detectors into a Euclidean form. The whitening operation thus removes hyperspectral

curvature and simplifies the algebraic computation of any given detection statistics.

The whitened form of the background data also suffices for the real time change detection algorithm that NRL uses. Experimental results describe below show that one can expect the whitened form of hyperspectral imagery from one day to constitute a good estimate of whitened data from the same scene on another. This and other details of the algorithm suite are elaborated below.

3. DETECTION ALGORITHMS

Static Detection

Let $\{x\}$ represent a mean-centered set of remotely sensed hyperspectral radiances. Each N -dimensional measurement x is associated with one ground pixel. In order to detect anomalous pixels, such as could arise from manmade objects, the WARHORSE system employs the RX [6] algorithm (often with a pre-processing step, discussed below).

RX generates an ellipsoidal decision surface in hyperspace (the N -dimensional vector space of hyperspectral data). It does a relatively poor job of segregating background from target pixels. Except for the finite-volume interior of the ellipsoid, all points in the exterior infinite-dimensional region are declared "target." The ellipsoid is constructed from an estimate of the background covariance matrix, viz.

$$X \equiv \langle xx^t \rangle, \quad (1)$$

where t indicates matrix transposition, and the brackets denote the sample mean value. (In WARHORSE, adaptive estimates of the local mean and covariance are generated as an airborne mission progresses—see §2.2.) All the algorithms used here are based, at least partially, on this covariance matrix. For example, static anomaly detection is often based solely on it (and implicitly on the mean value of x .)

The singular value decomposition (SVD) of X , a nonnegative symmetric matrix, finds its eigenvalues and eigenvectors (also called principal components), allowing it to be expressed as

$$X = \Lambda_X D_X \Lambda_X^t. \quad (2)$$

The columns of Λ_X are the eigenvectors, while entries of the diagonal matrix D_X are the eigenvalues of X . The RX decision surface is defined as an ellipsoid with principal axes whose directions are parallel to these eigenvectors, and whose lengths are proportional to the square roots of the eigenvalues. It can be thought of as a quadric fit to the

background data. Also, if the data are Gaussian, such an ellipsoid—if based on the true covariance matrix—is a locus of points of constant density function. The ellipsoid is defined by:

$$x^t X^{-1} x = \text{constant} . \quad (3)$$

Anomaly detection—

This equation also describes the decision surface of the RX detector, which declares a target when

$$x^t X^{-1} x > \text{constant} . \quad (4)$$

A common variant called SSRX ("Subspace RX") used in WARHORSE preprocesses the data by deleting a few of the high variance dimensions, i.e. projects each data point into a subspace defined by lower variance eigenvectors, and then applies RX. This is generally a superior detector to RX, whenever the distribution of target pixels in the deleted dimensions has smaller variance than the background pixels.

Matched Filter—

When an estimate T of a target's expected spectrum (relative the background mean) is available, a more selective detector, the linear matched filter (MF) can be constructed. The MF is also implemented in WARHORSE. This algorithm defines a hyperplanar decision surface

$$T^t X^{-1} x = \text{constant} , \quad (5)$$

which confines the target-decision region to a semi-infinite region. Research [3,5] into algorithms that generate even more selective regions is in progress, using data archived from the YOGI (see Section 4) mission.

A target is declared by the matched filter if

$$MF(x) \equiv T^t X^{-1} x > \text{constant} . \quad (6)$$

In hyperspectral applications, matched filters typically reduce false alarm rates below those of RX by one to two orders of magnitude.

Change Detection

Next we describe two algorithms for hyperspectral change detection. Because the goal is actually to distinguish unusual changes from those that might occur naturally, and over long periods of time (typically from a few hours to a few days), these methods are more appropriately described as anomalous change detectors. The most common application detects targets that have moved during the period between data collections. By focusing only on such targets, these methods usually produce lower false alarm

rates than any static detection scheme.

Just as RX and MF are anomaly- and signature-based detectors, respectively, so are there change detectors with analogous differences in assumed prior target knowledge.

Blind Change Detection with Chronochrome—

The Chronochrome Algorithm [7], which uses no signature information, is fundamentally a two-step procedure. Letting Equation (1) refer to data from time 1, and $\{y\}$ to a (mean-centered) time-2 data set, we define a covariance matrix analogous to (1), along with the cross-temporal covariance matrix C :

$$Y \equiv \langle yy^t \rangle, \quad C \equiv \langle yx^t \rangle. \quad (7)$$

The first step in Chronochrome is the least-mean-square error prediction of time-2 data from time-1 data

$$\hat{y}_{CC} = CX^{-1}x. \quad (8)$$

The second step applies the RX anomaly detector to the chronochrome (CC) prediction error

$$\mathcal{E}_{CC} \equiv \hat{y}_{CC} - y. \quad (9)$$

That is, the Chronochrome test for a changed target (see Equation (4)) is

$$\mathcal{E}_{CC}^t E_{CC}^{-1} \mathcal{E}_{CC} > \text{constant}, \quad (10)$$

where the chronochrome error covariance matrix is given by

$$E_{CC} \equiv \langle \mathcal{E}_{CC} \mathcal{E}_{CC}^t \rangle = Y - CX^{-1}C^t. \quad (11)$$

Matched Change Detection—

If the mean target signature is also available for use in change detection, then a multi-temporal version of the matched filter can be constructed. It should be expected to combine the detection gains of Chronochrome with those of static matched filtering.

To derive the algorithm, first form a composite signal z that is a stacked version of the time-1 and time-2 signals:

$$z = \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

If arrivals of the target at time 2 are to be detected, then the effective target signature for time 1 is the background mean (zero), but is some (presumed) known mean spectrum T_y (relative to the background mean) for time 2. Therefore, its

composite signature is

$$T_z = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ T_y \end{pmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

The composite covariance matrix is given by

$$Z \equiv \langle zz^t \rangle = \begin{pmatrix} \langle xx^t \rangle & \langle xy^t \rangle \\ \langle yx^t \rangle & \langle yy^t \rangle \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} X & C^t \\ C & Y \end{pmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

in which Z has been partitioned into its x - and y -components.

Therefore, a matched change detection (MCD) is declared when the composite matched filter produces a threshold exceedance:

$$\begin{aligned} MCD(z) &= T_z^t Z^{-1} z \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & T_y^t \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} X & C^t \\ C & Y \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} > \text{constant} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

MCD can be expected to perform best of all the algorithms described above, because it exploits in combination all the prior knowledge that they use: signature information and the occurrence of change.

Covariance Equalization

Neither MCD nor the Chronochrome algorithm is implemented as described above in the real time WARHORSE system, because of the difficulty in consistently achieving sub-pixel image registration for an operational airborne system. (However, see [4] for progress on this front.) This means that estimates of the cross-temporal covariance C (see (7)) matrix can suffer, and this is required for both change detectors described above. For example, Chronochrome detection can begin to degrade substantially after uncorrected misregistration of a few pixels.

Imperfect registration led to the development of an alternative form of predictor to CC in Equation (8) called Covariance Equalization (CE). CE is actually the entire class of linear predictors that generate estimates \hat{y} whose mean and covariance matrices are identical to those of the desired variable y . The general form for this class is easily derived.

A (mean centered) linear estimate \hat{y} is defined by a matrix L

$$\hat{y} = Lx. \quad (16)$$

This estimate has covariance matrix

$$\hat{Y} \equiv \langle \hat{y}\hat{y}^t \rangle = \langle Lxx^tL^t \rangle = LXL^t, \quad (17)$$

by Equation (1). The CE family is defined by the condition

$$\hat{Y} \equiv Y, \quad (18)$$

i.e.,

$$Y = LXL^t \quad (19)$$

The general solution to this quadratic matrix equation is

$$L = Y^2 \Lambda X^{-\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (20)$$

with Λ an arbitrary orthonormal matrix, i.e. $\Lambda\Lambda^t = I$ (the identity matrix). The square root of a matrix X is uniquely defined, and can be found from any SVD of it (although SVDs need not be unique). For example (see Equation (2))

$$X^{\frac{1}{2}} = \Lambda_X D_X^{\frac{1}{2}} \Lambda_X^t. \quad (21)$$

As discussed in [8], the convenient choice $\Lambda = I$ works well for hyperspectral applications. That is, the CE prediction

$$\hat{y}_{CE} = Y^2 X^{-\frac{1}{2}} x \quad (22)$$

(the hyperspectral version of CE) is nearly as accurate for hyperspectral data as the optimal prediction, given by Equation (8). Notice, however, that the CE prediction does not depend on cross-temporal image registration. For example, it does not depend on the matrix C .

Next we describe CE versions of three signal processing operations common in the WARHORSE sensing system.

Signature Evolution—

Because Covariance Equalization relates background pixels from different times nearly as well as the optimal transformation, it can be used to do the same for target spectra. Thus signatures collected on one day can be used to predict those on another (see Figure 4), with no registration requirements. In fact, as shown below, the effectiveness of CE in achieving this has been demonstrated across distant locations.

CE-based signature prediction followed by matched filtering is part of a common WARHORSE Concept of Operation. Targets detected on one day by, for example, an anomaly detector, can be detected much more easily—i.e.,

at reduced false alarm rate—on a second day, if they are present the second time in the same general type of background. The apparent target signatures evolve much as the environment does, and this is reflected by changes in the background mean and covariance matrix, the two statistics used to define the hyperspectral form of CE.

Approximate Chronochrome—

For similar reasons, the CE predictor can be inserted as a replacement for the first step of the Chronochrome algorithm, which is used for blind (i.e. with no target information) change detection. This can be valuable when registration to a level better than a typical background correlation length is problematical. There are two primary types of error in Chronochrome detection that are associated with misregistration.

The first, error in the estimate of the prediction matrix CX^{-1} , is caused by poor estimates of C (see Equation (7)). The second, computing the prediction error, suffers because the y of Equation (9) has to be associated with the x Equation (8). However, this can be a small effect when the background correlation length is greater than the misregistration. In this case, most clutter leakage occurs at object edges, and these can often be recognized and eliminated with simple shape filters.

A CE-based blind change detector can mitigate the first error by using the CE transform $Y^2 X^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ instead of CX^{-1} . First, define equations analogous to Equations (9) through (11), with the replacement (CC \rightarrow CE), then replace Equation (8) by Equation (22). Blind change detection can then be achieved by identifying (with the RX algorithm) anomalies in the statistic

$$\mathcal{E}_{CE} \equiv \hat{y}_{CE} - y. \quad (23)$$

Results of applying a real time version of this CE-based anomaly change detector are reported below.

Matched Change Detection with CE—

Finally, misregistration errors that degrade Matched Change Detection (Note that Equation (15) depends on the matrix C) also can be mitigated with the CE transformation. First we use the easily verified matrix identity

$$\begin{pmatrix} X & C^t \\ C & Y \end{pmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} (X - C^t Y^{-1} C)^{-1} & -X^{-1} C^t E_{CC}^{-1} \\ -Y^{-1} C (X - C^t Y^{-1} C)^{-1} & E_{CC}^{-1} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (24)$$

where E_{CC} , defined by Equation (11), satisfies

$$E_{CC} \equiv (Y - CX^{-1}C^t), \quad (25)$$

which follows from Equations (1), (7) - (9), and (11).

Using Schur's matrix inversion lemma [9]

$$(X - C^t Y^{-1} C)^{-1} = X^{-1} + X^{-1} C^t E_{CC}^{-1} C X^{-1}, \quad (26)$$

and inserting Equation (24) into Equation (15) produces

$$MCD(z) = T_y^t E_{CC}^{-1} \varepsilon_{CC} > \text{constant}, \quad (27)$$

where ε_{cc} is the chronochrome prediction error (Equation (9)).

Equation (27) facilitates an interpretation of MCD as a two-step procedure. First, find the least mean-squared-error prediction \hat{y}_{cc} of the pixel y , at time 2, from the corresponding pixel x at time 1. Then apply a matched filter to the error ε_{cc} (recall Equation (6), and note that E_{cc} is the covariance matrix of ε_{CC}). This entails the usual error induced by misregistration, because Equation (27) depends on an estimated value of C . However, the two-step interpretation suggests that we replace the chronochrome prediction step with one based on CE. That is, we replace Equation (27) with

$$MCD_{CE}(z) = T_y^t E_{CE}^{-1} \varepsilon_{CE} > \text{constant}, \quad (28)$$

which is the CE version of matched change detection. The error ε_{CE} is now that associated with the CE prediction

$$\varepsilon_{CE} \equiv \hat{y}_{CE} - y, \quad (29)$$

(see Equation (22)), as is the error covariance matrix E_{CE} , which can be derived from the measured statistics of the estimate. The matched filtering step remains unchanged.

4. WARHORSE DETECTION

Data Conditioning based on Covariance Equalization

The particular form (Equation (20) with $\Lambda=1$) of CE transformation that has been found accurate in hyperspectral applications lends itself to a convenient protocol for storing target signature and background spectra (for use in real time change detection). It also greatly simplifies much of the computation associated with detection algorithms by reducing many operations to simple dot products.

Define "whitened variables" by transforming all radiances linearly with the square root of the local estimate of the background covariance matrix. For example, let

$$\begin{aligned} x_w &\equiv X^{-\frac{1}{2}} x, & (T_x)_w &\equiv X^{-\frac{1}{2}} T_x, \\ y_w &\equiv Y^{-\frac{1}{2}} y, & (T_y)_w &\equiv Y^{-\frac{1}{2}} T_y \end{aligned}, \quad (30)$$

define whitened background and target variables at the two measurement times. We now show that all the CE-based detectors discussed above can be expressed simply, and in terms of whitened variables only.

The RX statistic (Equation (4)) trivially simplifies to

$$x_w^t x_w, \quad (31)$$

that is, a simple Euclidean measure. Also, the matched filter (Equation (5)) becomes a simple dot product, based on the whitened target signature:

$$(T_x)_w^t x_w. \quad (32)$$

Similarly, when target detection at time 2 uses a matched filter based on a signature derived from time 1 with CE, the statistic becomes

$$T_y^t Y^{-1} y = \left(\frac{1}{Y^2} X^{-\frac{1}{2}} T_x \right)^t Y^{-1} y = (T_x)_w^t y_w. \quad (33)$$

Thus, this detector also can be written in a form that depends only on whitened variables.

For the CE version of blind change detection, one computes the RX statistic for the CE prediction error:

$$\begin{aligned} &(\hat{y}_{CE} - y)^t E_{CE}^{-1} (\hat{y}_{CE} - y) \\ &= \left(Y^{\frac{1}{2}} X^{-\frac{1}{2}} x - y \right)^t E_{CE}^{-1} \left(Y^{\frac{1}{2}} X^{-\frac{1}{2}} x - y \right) \\ &= \left(Y^{\frac{1}{2}} x_w - Y^{\frac{1}{2}} y_w \right)^t E_{CE}^{-1} \left(Y^{\frac{1}{2}} x_w - Y^{\frac{1}{2}} y_w \right) \end{aligned}. \quad (34)$$

But note that the whitened difference

$$\varepsilon_w \equiv x_w - y_w \quad (35)$$

has covariance matrix

$$\begin{aligned}
E_w &\equiv \left\langle (x_w - y_w)(x_w - y_w)^T \right\rangle = \\
&\left\langle \left(X^{-\frac{1}{2}}x - Y^{-\frac{1}{2}}y \right) \left(X^{-\frac{1}{2}}x - Y^{-\frac{1}{2}}y \right)^T \right\rangle = \\
&Y^{-\frac{1}{2}} \left\langle \left(Y^{\frac{1}{2}}X^{-\frac{1}{2}}x - y \right) \left(Y^{\frac{1}{2}}X^{-\frac{1}{2}}x - y \right)^T \right\rangle Y^{-\frac{1}{2}} \\
&= Y^{-\frac{1}{2}} E_{CE} Y^{-\frac{1}{2}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

It follows immediately that Equation (34) is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned}
&(\hat{y}_{CE} - y)^T E_{CE}^{-1} (\hat{y}_{CE} - y) \\
&= (x_w - y_w)^T E_w^{-1} (x_w - y_w),
\end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

showing that the CE version of blind change detection can be achieved using only the difference of whitened variables along with the corresponding covariance matrix.

Finally, for signature-based CE change detection—MCD—(Equation (28)) can be written:

$$\begin{aligned}
MCD_{CE}(z) &= T_x^T E_{CE}^{-1} \epsilon_{CE} \\
&= \left(Y^{\frac{1}{2}} X^{-\frac{1}{2}} T_x \right)^T E_{CE}^{-1} (\hat{y}_{CE} - y) \\
&= \left(Y^{\frac{1}{2}} (T_x)_w \right)^T E_{CE}^{-1} \left(Y^{\frac{1}{2}} X^{-\frac{1}{2}} x - Y^{\frac{1}{2}} y_w \right) \\
&= (T_x)_w^T Y^{\frac{1}{2}} E_{CE}^{-1} Y^{\frac{1}{2}} (x_w - y_w).
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

From Equation (36), it follows that Equation (38) is

equivalent to

$$MCD_{CE}(z) = (T_x)_w^T E_w^{-1} \epsilon_w. \tag{39}$$

Therefore, the CE version of matched change detection can be written as a standard matched filter based on a whitened target spectrum and operating on a whitened error signal.

In summary, we have shown that all the detection algorithms discussed here can be implemented by a real time system that archives and operates on only the whitened versions of targets and backgrounds. This is the fundamental motivator of the current WARHORSE DPC signal processing architecture [4] (Figure 1).

We remark that some advanced algorithms require the full covariance matrix of the background. For example, subspace methods [5] may distinguish between high- and low-variance background dimensions. The whitening process erases such information. However, the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the covariance matrix encode its entire information content. Because in WARHORSE, the covariance matrix is updated as often as a new block is ingested, this is also how often the N eigenvectors and eigenvalues (N is the number of digitized wavelengths) of the covariance matrix need to be recorded. And we note these quantities are routinely computed anyway in order to

compute the whitening matrix $X^{-\frac{1}{2}}$.

YOGI Experiments

The YOGI exercise is discussed in detail in several references [1,3,4]. A total of 15 camo nets were deployed at two sites in Montana. WARHORSE waterfall displays showing detections, with target truth overlaid, appear in Figure 3. As expected, the detection algorithms using target signature information (CEMF is a matched filter based on a signature evolved with CE) produces fewer false alarms. Note, however, that this was based on a signature collected on a previous day. (See the blue and black curves of

Figure 3. WARHORSE Run 2003.07.29.15.48. “Touch” scoring with minimum 3m x 3m target cluster. Truth masks generated from NRL survey (purple). Detector outputs in green: SSRX (Left) and CEMF (right).

Figure 4.) Figure 5 shows detection performance for the anomaly detector SSRX, and also compares matched filtering results using the raw target spectrum to the CE-evolved version.

Change detection experiments were also conducted with the YOGI data. These produced excellent results in all cases, with MCD producing 100% detection probability at zero false alarm rate. An additional benefit of MCD accrues from its linearity: It treats target departures as if they were arrivals with negative signatures, thus permitting one to distinguish between the two types of change by using a lower as well as upper threshold.

Shortly after the YOGI exercise in Montana, NRL continued experiments with the same spectral targets at Ft. Benning, Georgia. Instead of using SSRX as a preliminary blind target detector, a matched filter was used, using a target signature evolved from the Montana data. The spectral predictions are compared in Figure 6. The utility of this procedure for target detection is documented in Figure 7, where matched filtering based on a CE-evolved signature—from Montana to Georgia—reproduces ROC performance of a matched filter derived from the in-scene signature.

5. SUMMARY

We have reported real time hyperspectral detection performance in WARHORSE by applying its algorithm suite to large volumes of data collected at the YOGI exercise. The continuing utility found in the principle of Covariance Equalization has led to evolutionary changes in the system signal processing architecture. Target and background spectra are transformed using local estimates of the hyperspectral first and second-order background statistics before being stored. This allows a greatly simplified computation for all five detection algorithms described above. The false alarm rates appear to be the lowest ever reported in such large data sets for real time onboard autonomous hyperspectral detection of manmade objects. We have also derived the mathematical form for a new detection algorithm, Matched Change Detection, as well as a CE version of it. MCD appears to be the most discriminating method of detecting the arrival or departure of targets using only spectral signatures that have been gathered in an earlier hyperspectral mission.

6. REFERENCES

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Figure 4 . Predicting one spectrum (black) from that on a brighter day (blue) using Covariance Equalization (red).

Figure 5. Recorded WARHORSE data played through real time signal processor. Cue from SSRX used to capture signature and detect target one day later with matched filter using unmodified (SSRX) and CE-evolved (CEMF) spectrum.

Figure 6. Evolution of Net Signature: Montana to Ft. Benning. CE-evolved signature captures stronger absorption features of the Georgia atmosphere.

Figure 7. CE evolution of Montana training signature to Ft. Benning conditions duplicates in-scene matched filter performance at low false alarm rates.

BIOGRAPHY

Dr. Alan Schaum received a Ph.D. in Theoretical Physics in 1978 from The Johns Hopkins University, where his research focused on relativistic quantum field theory. Until 1983 he applied queuing and information theories to network planning problems at Bell Laboratories in Holmdel, New Jersey. For the past 21 years at The Naval Research Laboratory in Washington, he has developed signal and image processing methods in support of intelligence operations. His current research emphasizes multivariate detection theory and the modeling of hyperspectral terrestrial background signatures and their dynamics

